

Low-cost Streamflow Monitoring using Timelapse Imagery and Machine Learning Models

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by

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1 Introduction

Continuous streamflow monitoring is essential for advancing our understanding of the hydrology and ecology of aquatic ecosystems, as well as for making sound management decisions to preserve, protect, and restore these ecosystems. However, collecting streamflow data can be challenging due to the cost and skillset required to install, operate and maintain traditional streamflow gauges. As a result, there is a substantial data gap of streamflow data for smaller streams and headwater systems that comprise over half of the total stream length in the United States. To address this monitoring gap, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) and U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) have developed a database and machine learning platform called the Flow Photo Explorer (FPE) for estimating streamflow conditions using timelapse imagery collected by low-cost trail cameras (USGS, 2025a).

Recent advances in artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) algorithms now enable use of timelapse imagery to estimate environmental conditions such as streamflow was made possible by. Traditionally, computer vision AI/ML models require labelled training data in which each input (e.g., timelapse image) is labelled using the associated value of the target response variable (e.g., streamflow). From this labelled training data, the model learns how to predict the response (streamflow) for a given input (image). However, creating this dataset would require measuring streamflow using a gauge collocated with the camera collecting the images.

Recent research has demonstrated a novel approach to this problem by using a rank-based AI/ML model that can be trained without the need to collect any observed streamflow measurements, thus making this method more accessible and less costly (Gupta et al., 2022). With this approach, the model is trained using a dataset comprised of annotated image pairs; for each image pair, a human is tasked with indicating which of two images appears to have more flow. From these annotated image pairs, the model is trained to effectively learn how to sort a set of images from low to high flow by generating a numeric value (“score”) for each image representing the relative amount of flow. By associating each score with the timestamp of its corresponding image, the predicted scores can be combined into a continuous timeseries reflecting relative changes in flow over time.

The overall goal of this project was to develop and implement this rank-based AI/ML deep learning model for estimating streamflow using timelapse imagery and human-generated training data, and without the need for collocated streamflow gauges. Preliminary research demonstrated the feasibility of this modeling approach using simulated annotation data (Gupta et al., 2022); however, many questions remained regarding the robustness and transferability of this approach across a wide range of sites and conditions using human-generated annotations. Therefore, the purpose of this project was to investigate these questions by performing a variety of experiments and sensitivity analyses, and to develop guidelines for the collection of both the timelapse imagery and human annotations optimized to ensure model results are sufficiently accurate and reliable.

In addition to the development of the modeling methodology, this project also aimed to make this model widely accessible by integrating it into the existing USGS Flow Photo Explorer (FPE) platform (<https://www.usgs.gov/apps/ecosheds/fpe>), which has been under development since 2019. Since its inception, FPE has provided USEPA, USGS, and project partners with an accessible, web-based data repository for storing and managing timelapse imagery, observed hydrologic data, and associated metadata. Through this project, the AI/ML model has been integrated into FPE by 1) providing a new interface for users to generate pairwise annotations of their images, and 2) streamlining the model training and application process for generating estimated relative streamflow, the results of which are now publicly accessible through the FPE platform. In this report, we describe the development and application of the model methodology as well as its integration into the FPE platform. All work was completed in accordance with the project Quality Assurance Protection Plan (QAPP) (L-ICSD-0034150-QP-1-0).

2 Data Sources

The primary data source for this project was the FPE database, which is a relational database that stores timelapse images, streamflow data, and associated metadata at individual monitoring stations belonging to registered FPE users. Since the FPE database was publicly released in October 2021, it has grown to 389 stations with nearly 7.8 million images from over 200 users representing federal, state, tribal agencies and non-profit organizations (Table 1, Figure 1). The total number of images has been growing exponentially, doubling once every 302 days on average since Jan 2023. After adding the annotation interface to the FPE website in mid-2023, FPE users have annotated over half a million image pairs. Using those annotations, we have trained 56 individual AI/ML models at individual stations beginning in April 2024, the results of which are presented in Section 4 below.

Table 1: Current size of each primary table in the FPE database as of Jan 28, 2025.

Table	# Rows
Users	229
Stations	389
Images	7,780,094
Flow Measurements	2,044,873
Annotations	582,612
Flow Models	56

Figure 1: Cumulative growth and additions to the USGS FPE database since Oct 2021.

2.1.1 Timelapse Imagery

For each station, the timelapse imagery contains digital photos of a stream or river collected from a fixed location at regular time intervals between 15 and 60 minutes. Each image file must be in JPG format and contain valid EXIF (Exchangeable Image File Format) metadata. The image files themselves are stored in a cloud-based file storage system (AWS Simple Storage System, S3), while the metadata of those files are stored in the FPE database.

Image metadata includes information about where the images were taken including the station latitude/longitude and type of water body, as well as a description of the general methodology used to deploy the timelapse camera including information about the camera type and the time zone associated with the image timestamps. Additional metadata about each image (e.g., dimensions, resolution, timestamp) is automatically extracted from the EXIF data embedded within each image file by the FPE platform when users upload their images.

2.1.2 Measured Streamflow Data

To evaluate model accuracy and performance, observed streamflow data are also collected at some stations at the same location as the timelapse camera. Observed streamflow was obtained from one of two sources:

1. **USGS National Water Information System (NWIS):** for stations collocated with a USGS streamflow gauge, observed streamflow data were directly retrieved from the USGS NWIS data portal (USGS, 2025b). These stations were identified as having a

user-provided NWIS ID as part of the station metadata. Streamflow data for these stations were downloaded directly from NWIS and then integrated with the FPE image dataset.

2. **FPE Database:** for stations not collocated with a USGS streamflow gauge, FPE users can also (optionally) upload observed streamflow data directly to FPE. These observed datasets include metadata including the associated station, the timestamp time zone, missing value indicators (e.g., -9999), measurement units, flags, and a general description of the equipment and methodology used to collect these data as required by FPE. When available, these datasets were retrieved directly from the FPE database and integrated with the timelapse imagery.

All observed streamflow used in this project collected in accordance with an EPA-approved QAPP or similar standard operating procedure (SOP) document such as the USGS streamflow monitoring protocols.

2.1.3 Human Annotations of Image Pair Rankings

For each station, a dataset containing pairwise image comparisons indicating which of two images should be ranked higher based on the apparent streamflow was required. These image comparisons were done by human annotators using the FPE annotation interface, which was created to support this project (Figure 2).

The FPE annotation interface allows the user to select a station and enter the number of image pairs they wish to annotate. They can also (optionally) specify a start and end date from which the images are sampled, as well as a range of times during the day. The interface then generates a randomized sample of image pairs among all available images for the selected station. The annotator is then tasked with determining which of the two images appears to contain greater streamflow. The annotator can choose from four options: the left image, the right image, about the same, or unknown. The unknown annotation can be used if the annotator is unable to make a determination, usually because one or both images is not of sufficient quality or clarity (e.g., hazy, dark, glare, etc.). In addition to specifying the ranking of the pair, the user can also annotate each individual image based on whether it contains ice/snow, is a fully or partially dry streambed, or is a “bad” image indicating poor visibility. However, these additional annotations are not used for the current model, and are being collected as additional labels for the future development of image classification models.

All annotations were generated by staff and interns from USEPA, USGS, and other project partners. Annotators were required to have a user account with FPE in order to track their progress and to support the quality review process. Annotations were not generated by any public or anonymous users.

Photo Annotator

Stations Search

Priority stations are those we are actively seeking more annotations for. Please annotate those first unless there are others you are specifically interested in. Once a station has at least 2,000 *daytime* annotations, please move on to another.

Station	# Annotations (Total)	↑ # Annotations (Daytime)	↓ Priority
Green River_01170100	6825	6820	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fenton River	7405	7405	<input type="checkbox"/>
West Brook_0_01171100	11068	8880	<input type="checkbox"/>
Browns Brook	11158	11158	<input type="checkbox"/>
East Branch Eightmile River	11290	11290	<input type="checkbox"/>

Rows per page: 386-390 of 390

Instructions

- Select a station on the table (priority stations first, if possible), then enter the number of photo pairs you would like to annotate and specify the minimum/maximum hours and dates (optional). Then click **Start Annotating**.
- For each pair of photos:
 - First, review each photo individually and indicate if that photo shows one of the following conditions by clicking the appropriate button below the photo.
 - Dry**: stream is completely dry (no water visible)
 - Disconnected**: stream is partially dry with disconnected pools of water
 - Partial Ice/Snow**: stream is partially covered by ice/snow (can see some water)
 - Full Ice/Snow**: stream is fully covered by ice/snow (cannot see any water)
 - Bad Photo**: cannot see water because the photo is not clear (e.g., blurry, too dark, glare)
 - Next, determine which of the two shows more water, and click the appropriate button below the photo pair (**Left** or **Right**). Select **About the Same** if the photos show similar amounts of water, or **Don't Know** if you cannot make a valid comparison (e.g., one or both is a bad photo or the camera angle is too inconsistent). You can also use the following keyboard shortcuts to make your selection: **j** = Left, **k** = About the Same, **l** = Right, **m** = Don't Know.
 - If you were unsure about your selection or had any other questions or observations about this pair of photos, let us know in the **Comments** field.
 - When finished with this pair, click **Next** (or press your Enter key) to load the next pair of photos and repeat these steps.
- When you are finished, click the **Submit** button to save your annotations to the server.
- If you need to stop early, go ahead and submit the annotations you have already completed.
- Once you have completed a batch of annotations, you can do another batch by repeating step 1 above.

Number of photo pairs:

The following inputs are optional, and should only be used when requested. Leave blank for defaults, which will include only daytime photos (7:00 am to 6:59 pm) from any available date at the selected station.

Minimum Photo Hour

Integer (0-23) in 24H time (default = 7 for 7:00 AM)

Maximum Photo Hour

Integer (0-23) in 24H time (default = 18 for 6:59 PM)

Minimum Photo Date

YYYY-MM-DD format (default = first available)

Maximum Photo Date

YYYY-MM-DD format (default = last available)

START ANNOTATING >

RCNX0014.JPG
Jan 3, 2024 1:30:00 PM EST

DRY

DISCONNECTED

PARTIAL ICE/SNOW

FULL ICE/SNOW

BAD PHOTO

03180516.JPG
Mar 18, 2023 12:15:01 PM EDT

DRY

DISCONNECTED

PARTIAL ICE/SNOW

FULL ICE/SNOW

BAD PHOTO

Which photo has more water?

LEFT (J)

ABOUT THE SAME (K)

RIGHT (L)

DON'T KNOW (M)

Any comments?

< PREV

Pair 2 of 100
(2.0% complete)

NEXT (ENTER) >

SUBMIT

Figure 2: Screenshot of the FPE annotation interface.

3 Methodology

An artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) deep learning model was developed to estimate relative streamflow using timelapse imagery. The model is based on a learning-to-rank (RankNet) framework, which is a supervised machine learning technique for performing pairwise regression (Burges et al., 2005). Unlike other AI/ML regression models that are trained to estimate the value of some property (i.e., streamflow) for each input feature (i.e., image), RankNet models are trained using pairs of input features that are labelled based on which of the two inputs has a higher rank (e.g., which of two images has more streamflow). Through this training, the model learns to generate a numerical “score” for each image that can be used to effectively sort the images from lowest to highest rank (the images with the lowest and highest scores are predicted to have the lowest and highest flows, respectively).

This project builds on previous research by Gupta et al. (2022), which first demonstrated the feasibility of using a RankNet model to estimate streamflow from timelapse imagery at a single monitoring station. For that initial research, the pairwise image comparisons (i.e., which of two images has more flow) used to train the model were generated using observed streamflow data collected by data loggers deployed at each station. As a result, the training dataset contained the observed streamflow associated with each image. However, using observed streamflow data to label image pairs for model training substantially limits the applicability and accessibility of this method as it would require installation of both a traditional streamflow gage and a timelapse camera at each station. In this project, we extended the initial research by Gupta et al. (2022) to develop a model training methodology that does not require measuring streamflow with a gauge collocated with the timelapse camera.

Instead of using directly observed streamflow, the FPE model is trained using annotated image pairs generated by users through the FPE website. Using the FPE annotation interface, each image pair is annotated by a registered user, who indicates which of the two images appears to have more streamflow. Using this approach, the only required training data are the image pair annotations generated by FPE users, the goal of which is to eliminate the need to collect streamflow data in the field. The trained model is then used to generate a timeseries of predicted scores based on the full set of timelapse imagery at the corresponding station. The percentile ranks of these scores represent the relative amount of flow on a scale from 0 to 100% (with the 0%-tile image having the lowest flow, and the 100%-tile image having the highest).

A flow diagram shows the major model components and sequence for training and applying the model at a single station (Figure 3). Figure 3 does not include model evaluation, which is a separate process performed only for stations at which observed data are available. Ultimately, the modeling methodology developed for this project was designed for locations where observed flow are not available.

Figure 3: Diagram of the FPE image, annotation and model workflow.

3.1 Model Training

Model training was conducted using a standard back-propagation algorithm, which is commonly used for training neural networks, based on a binary cross entropy cost function to compute training loss (see Gupta et al., 2022 for details). Prior to training, the pairwise image comparison dataset was randomly divided into two subsets referred to as the train and validation splits. Approximately 80% of the annotation dataset was assigned to the train split, and the remaining 20% to the validation split. Only the annotations in the train split were used by the back-propagation algorithm to fine-tune the model parameters. The validation split was used to compute accuracy (i.e., loss) of the model in predicting pairwise rankings using image pairs not included in the training.

The overall loss of each split was then computed at the end of each training iteration (i.e., epoch), which represents one full pass of the training data. Multiple epochs are commonly used to train neural network models by exposing the model to the same dataset (although in different, randomized orders) repeatedly. For each station, training was performed over a series of at least 20 epochs. The epoch with the minimum validation loss was then selected as the final trained model, which is subsequently used to predict the scores of all images at that station.

Each model was trained only using daytime images captured between 7am and 7pm (local time). Although some camera models provide capabilities for capturing nighttime images using infrared (IR) illumination, the quality of these images varied widely between stations. Therefore, to ensure consistency between stations, only daytime images were used for model training.

3.2 Model Predictions

After a model was successfully trained for a given station, it was used to generate predictions of all available timelapse images at that station. For each image, the model predicts a numeric value called the score. Although the scale and distribution of the scores

do not have any direct physical interpretation, they can be used to represent the relative amount of streamflow (or other hydrologic parameter) based on their ranks. For example, the image with the lowest score is predicted to have the lowest streamflow, while that with the highest score has the highest streamflow. Raw scores generated by each model were normalized by subtracting the mean and dividing the standard deviation such that the resulting values approximated a standard normal distribution (mean = 0, st. dev. = 1).

The scores were also converted to rank percentiles on a scale of 0% (lowest) to 100% (highest) by:

$$P_i = (\text{rank}[S_i] - 1) / (n - 1) \times 100\%$$

where P_i is the rank percentile of image i (0 to 100%), S_i is the predicted score of image i , and n is the total number of images. The rank() function returns the rank of S_i among the scores of all images and ranges from 1 (lowest) to n (highest).

By combining the normalized value and rank percentile of each predicted score with the timestamp of its corresponding image, the final model output dataset comprises a continuous timeseries of relative streamflow scaled to both a standard normal distribution and percentile ranges from 0 to 100% for the associated station. In addition to generating continuous timeseries based on the individual image scores, daily timeseries were also generated for each model by calculating the daily means of the normalized scores.

3.3 Model Evaluation

At stations with available streamflow data, the accuracy and performance of each model was evaluated by comparing the predicted image scores against measured flows. Model evaluation was performed using both graphic and statistical methods. Graphical methods included various exploratory data analysis (EDA) plots comparing the temporal dynamics and distributions of the observed and predicted data in order to identify areas where the model may be potentially biased or have high uncertainty or inaccuracy. The goodness-of-fit of the model predictions was also evaluated using the Kendall's tau statistic, which is a non-parametric measure of correlation based on the ranking of a paired dataset.

Each model was evaluated based on four subsets of all available images:

1. **Training Images:** images included in the training split of the annotation pairs
2. **Validation Images:** images included in the validation split of the annotation pairs
3. **Test-In Images:** images not included in the training or validation pairs but captured during the period spanned by the annotation pairs; these images are considered “in-distribution” test images as they occur during the same period of time as the training and validation images.
4. **Test-Out Images:** images captured after the period over which annotations were generated; these images are considered “out-of-distribution” test images as they occur during a period that is distinct from the period containing the training and validation images and pairs.

Kendall's tau was computed for each image subset, and for all images combined. As with model training, predictions for model evaluation were only generated for daytime images (7am – 7pm) due to the variability in image quality between stations with IR-enabled cameras (see Section 3.1).

4 Results

4.1 Monitoring Stations

As of January 2025, the FPE model was trained and applied to 54 public stations and 4 private¹ stations. Stations and associated models at the 4 private stations are not included in this report to protect data privacy. Of the public stations, most are located in the Mid-Atlantic and Northeast regions, with a few additional stations located in Illinois, Oklahoma, Colorado, and Nevada (Figure 4). Sample images show mostly small, headwater streams, although a few stations are located on larger rivers (e.g., 146-Red River new Terra) (Figure 5). A list of these stations including a summary of the images and annotations used for training is provided in Appendix A.

Figure 4: Map of public FPE stations with trained models. Red = stations with both images and observed streamflow measurements, Blue = stations with only images.

¹ FPE users have the option to designate any of their stations as private, in which the station and any associated images, data, and model results are not publicly shown on the FPE website, nor included in this report.

Figure 5: Sample images from FPE stations with trained models.

4.2 Human Annotations

The model was trained using between 723 and 10,211 human annotations of image pair rankings across the 54 public stations. Annotations by one user had been flagged in the database and were thus excluded due to accuracy concerns. Among those 54 stations, 32 stations had observed streamflow measurements for at least some image pairs, and provided opportunities to evaluate the annotations based on the true relative difference in flows of each pair.

Comparisons between the user-assigned pair rank (LEFT, SAME, or RIGHT) and the measured streamflow associated with each image shows that, in general, users tended to select “About the Same” (“SAME”) when the flows of the two images were relatively similar (i.e., blue points in Figure 6 tend to fall on the 1:1 line) (Figure 6). These comparisons reveal some errors where the user selected LEFT or RIGHT, but the actual measured streamflow indicated the opposite ranking (e.g., green points above the 1:1 line, or red points below).

To better understand the precision and accuracy of the human annotations, and evaluate whether there were differences between stations or users, we quantified the rates of these metrics, which we defined as:

- **Annotation Precision:** how often a user selects either LEFT or RIGHT but not SAME (indicates when users are able to discern a difference in flow between two images)
- **Annotation Accuracy:** given that the user selects either LEFT or RIGHT, how often are they correct compared to the true ranking based on the measured streamflow of the two images

Based on the annotations of all stations with observed flow data (111,764 pairs at 34 stations), the overall precision and accuracy were 81.6% and 71.8%, respectively. Across the individual stations, precision ranged from 36.5% to 99.7% (median = 86.9%) and accuracy ranged from 36.1% to 87.0% (median = 76.5%) (Figure 7).

A visual comparison between the two metrics shows that they are positively correlated over their full range of values (Figure 8). Stations with lower annotation precision also tended to have lower accuracy. However, this correlation was primarily driven by 3 stations with low precision and accuracy (< 60%). Among the other 29 stations, this correlation was no longer apparent. This suggests that some stations are more challenging to annotate than others as users have more difficulty discerning any difference in flow (precision) as well as accurately choosing which image has more apparent flow when they do think they can tell the difference (accuracy).

Figure 6: Scatterplots of human generated annotations at stations with observed streamflow measurements

Figure 7: Annotation accuracy and precision by station. Vertical lines denote overall values computed using all annotations.

Figure 8: Comparison of annotation accuracy and precision by station.

The precision and accuracy of a given image pair was also found to be related to the relative difference in measured flows between the two images, which was calculated by dividing the absolute difference by the mean of the two flows. When there was a small relative difference in the flows of two images, users were more likely to either indicate they had about the same flow, or to choose the incorrect image.

To quantify these relationships, logistic regression models for the annotation precision and accuracy rates based on the relative flow differences were fit using the annotations of each station, as well as for all annotations combined. The predicted probabilities of a precise (choosing Left or Right, but not Same) or accurate (choosing Left or Right correctly) annotation both increased with increasing relative flow (Figure 9). The largest increases occurred over relative flows from 0 to 100% with overall precision increasing from 60% to 94% using all stations, and overall accuracy increasing from 84 to 88%. However, among 25 of the 32 stations, predicted accuracy increased to >90% by the time relative flow difference reached 100%. Differences between the fitted logistic regression models also indicate variations in precision and accuracy among the different stations, suggesting some stations are harder to annotate than others.

Figure 9: Predicted probabilities from logistic regression models of annotation accuracy and precision as a function of relative flow difference. Black lines = each station, Red line = all stations combined.

In addition to comparing annotation precision and accuracy across the different stations, we also compared these across different users (Figure 10). User accuracy and precision both ranged from 31 to 100% with medians of 74.1% and 85.2%, respectively. Similar to station accuracy, users that were more precise, also tended to be more accurate (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Annotation accuracy and precision by user. Vertical lines denote overall values computed using all annotations.

Figure 11: Comparison of annotation accuracy and precision by user.

Lastly, to get a sense of the variability of precision and accuracy among different users for the same station, as well as for different stations by the same user, the two metrics were also calculated for each unique combination of user and station (Figure 12). Some stations were annotated by many users (up to 17 at 36-Mount Hope River), while others were annotated by only one user. Similarly, some users annotated multiple stations (up to 10 by user ff9b2), while others annotated only one station. Another figure of this same data shows a wide variation across users within each station (Figure 13). Therefore, variations in precision and accuracy across different stations are likely related, at least in part, to differences between the users who annotated each station. However, a review of the timelapse images at each of these stations suggested that accuracy may also be related to image quality as well as the stability of the camera field of view. Stations with multiple, large shifts in perspective tended to have lower precision and accuracy.

Figure 12: Annotation precision and accuracy for each unique pair of users and stations.

Figure 13: Annotation precision and accuracy of individual users at each station.

4.3 Model Predictions

The continuous and daily mean timeseries of predicted image scores show that the model predictions captured seasonal and event-based hydrologic patterns consistent with those typically associated with streamflow in the mid-Atlantic and Northeast regions of the United States (Figure 14). For example, higher flows tended to occur in winter and spring, and lower flows in summer. Many of the daily timeseries exhibit common hydrograph behavior, with a sharp rise in score indicating the start of a runoff event followed by a gradual decline (i.e., hydrograph recession) (e.g., 46-PA_06FL, lower right panel on first page of Figure 14).

Most stations show substantially higher short-term variability in the instantaneous scores compared to the daily means. In some cases, this variability changes over the course of the timeseries, with greater variability during one season than during another (e.g., high variability in winter 2020 at 34-Pendleton Hill Brook, row 4, column 2 of Figure 14). Closer inspection of this short-term variability showed that during these periods instantaneous flows tended to exhibit a diurnal pattern, which is not typically observed in natural streamflow during winter months when evapotranspiration is minimal.

For example, at 34-Pendleton Hill Brook, predicted image scores were substantially lower prior to 8am or after 4pm during the first 10 days of January 2020 (Figure 15). A review of the images during this period showed that the early morning and late afternoon images were taken before sunrise and after sunset when the camera had switched to infrared mode. Therefore, the model was not able to predict accurate flows for these darker images taken outside of daylight hours. Currently, our methodology attempts to remove all infrared/night time images by excluding any taken between 7pm – 7am. However, due to the shorter daylight hours during winter (especially in the northeast), these screening criteria do not always exclude all unwanted images, resulting in diurnal patterns related to the daily daytime period. Future revisions of this methodology will allow for dynamic night-time screening criteria by using either seasonally varying daylight times and/or the detection of night time images based on RGB characteristics of each image (i.e., if the image is in grayscale, then assume it is an infrared image that should be excluded).

Figure 14: Timeseries of predicted instantaneous and daily mean image scores.

Figure 14 (cont'd): Timeseries of predicted instantaneous and daily mean image scores.

Figure 14 (cont'd): Timeseries of predicted instantaneous and daily mean image scores.

Figure 15: Timeseries and diurnal pattern of predicted image scores at 34-Pendleton Hill Brook, Jan 1-10 2020, with sample images at 11am and 6pm on Jan 1.

Another cause of diurnal patterns is solar glare, which can occur at the same time of each day and cause inaccurate predictions of images with poor quality. An example of this is shown for a 9-day period at 29-West Brook 0_01171100 in November 2022 (Figure 16). At approximately 2pm on each, there is a large spike in the predicted image score due to the solar glare. Future work will include developing additional image screening algorithms for identifying and removing images with solar glare or other visual quality issues such as haziness.

Figure 16: Timeseries and diurnal pattern of predicted image scores at 29-West Brook 0_01171100, Nov 17-25 2020, with sample image at 2pm and 6pm on Nov 18.

4.4 Model Evaluation

The model predictions were evaluated at 33 of the 54 public stations where measured streamflow data were available. The accuracy of the model was primarily tested using the Kendall's tau statistic, which is a non-parametric measure of correlation based on the rankings of predicted scores and measured flows. Kendall's tau was calculated for each image split (*train*, *val*, *test-in*, *test-out*) as well as for all images (*all*) at each station (see Section 3.3). It was also calculated based on the daily (daytime, 7am-7pm) mean of the predicted scores and associated streamflow². For the daily timeseries, the image splits during the training period were grouped into one single split (*train/val/test-in*) since each date could contain images taken from one or more of those splits, and compared to dates during the out-of-distribution testing period (*test-out*) as well as using all images (*all*).

Based on the image scores, the distributions of Kendall's tau were highest for the *train* split (median = 0.767), followed by the *val* (0.759) and *test-in* (0.728) splits (Figure 17a). The *test-out* split, which represents model accuracy based on images taken outside the training period, had a lower range of values than the other splits (median = 0.647). For all images at each station the median Kendall's tau was 0.717 and ranged from 0.416 to 0.830. The lower tau values for the test-out split are due to the combination of:

1. Potential overfitting whereby the model learns visual patterns that are unique to the specific training period (e.g., patterns of vegetation growth)
2. Differences in the variability of flows during the *test-out* and training periods, which had different durations. Because the *test-out* periods tended to be shorter than the training periods, the overall variability in flows tended to be smaller. With less flow variability during the *test-out* period, the value of tau was more sensitive to small errors (i.e., noise) in the predictions compared to the training period when similar levels of noise would be masked by larger overall changes in flows. In other words, the *test-out* period tended to have a lower signal-to-noise ratio, which caused the value of tau to be more sensitive to random variations in the predictions.

Based on the daily mean scores, the distributions of Kendall's tau were relatively similar across the three splits with medians of 0.767, 0.753 and 0.751 for the *train/val/test-in*, *test-out*, and *all* splits, respectively (Figure 17b). The similarity between these splits suggests the models do not suffer from overfitting at a daily timestamp, at least for most stations. This observation supports the observation above that lower tau values for the test-out split of continuous image scores (Figure 17a) was thus likely due to the latter cause (shorter period, narrower distribution).

² Daily mean flows were computed using the flows associated the same images for which daily mean scores were computed. Therefore, daily mean flows were based on the same daytime period as the image scores, and not the full 24-hour period.

Figure 17: Distributions of Kendall's tau across stations for each image split based on image scores and daily mean scores.

A heatmap showing the tau value for each station and image split shows that only a few of the stations had substantially lower tau values in the *test-out* split (Figure 18). Most of these low tau values were based on relatively small sample sizes (either number of images or number of days) (Figure 19). Therefore, the lower tau values for *test-out* splits primarily reflects the limited range of observed flows during the testing period of each station.

Figure 18: Heatmap of Kendall's tau for each station and image split based on instantaneous image scores and daily mean scores. Missing values for test-out indicate stations for which the entire imagery period was annotated.

Figure 19: Comparison between Kendall's tau and the number of images and days for each station and image/daily mean split.

Timeseries and scatterplots of the daily mean predicted scores and observed flows show generally good agreement between the two (Figure 20). For these plots, the observed flows were first \log_{10} -transformed and then normalized by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation. The normalization of both variables allows for more direct visual comparison between the predicted scores and observed flows.

However, because observed flows are not used in model training, there is no expectation that the underlying distribution of predicted scores would have the same shape as observed flows, even after normalization. While both variables are approximately normally distributed, observed flows tend to have slightly longer tails, which is especially evident at the lowest flows. For example, the timeseries and scatterplots for 29-West Brook 0_01171100 suggest that the daily scores overpredict the lowest flows in summer 2022 (top right panel of Figure 20). However, these differences simply reflect a longer tail in the distribution of observed flows. On a relative basis, the two variables are more consistent with the lowest predicted scores being associated with the lowest observed flows. Therefore, when comparing the normalized scores and observed flows, it is important to recognize that the two should not be expected to always align.

In addition to normalization, predicted scores and observed flows can also be compared based on their rank percentiles (0 to 100%) (Figure 21). Unlike the normalized values, the rank percentiles are more directly comparable and are expected to align under optimal model performance. Furthermore, the comparisons of rank percentiles are more closely related to the Kendall's tau statistic, which is calculated based on those ranks, than the normalized values. However, the limitation of comparing rank percentiles is that they make it more difficult to evaluate the relative magnitudes of peak flows, which tend to have similar ranks (e.g., > 99%) across events even if the actual flows vary by multiple factors or even orders of magnitude.

Figure 20: Timeseries and scatterplots of normalized daily mean predicted score and observed flow for each station. Stations are sorted from highest to lowest Kendall's tau.

Figure 20 (cont'd): Timeseries and scatterplots of normalized daily mean predicted score and observed flow for each station. Stations are sorted from highest to lowest Kendall's tau.

Figure 20 (cont'd): Timeseries and scatterplots of normalized daily mean predicted score and observed flow for each station. Stations are sorted from highest to lowest Kendall's tau.

Figure 21: Timeseries and scatterplots of rank percentiles for daily mean predicted score and observed flow of each station. Stations are sorted from highest to lowest Kendall's tau.

Figure 21 (cont'd): Timeseries and scatterplots of rank percentiles for daily mean predicted score and observed flow of each station. Stations are sorted from highest to lowest Kendall's tau.

Figure 21 (cont'd): Timeseries and scatterplots of rank percentiles for daily mean predicted score and observed flow of each station. Stations are sorted from highest to lowest Kendall's tau.

4.5 FPE Integration

The model predictions of all 54 models were integrated into the FPE platform for viewing and exploration through the Photo Explorer interface (Figure 22). After selecting a station, users can view the timeseries of predicted image scores using either the original values or the rank percentiles. When available, observed streamflow data can also be viewed on the same chart for comparison. By default, the timeseries chart shows the daily mean values of each variable. However, the continuous, sub-daily timeseries can also be viewed by zooming in to a period less than 30 days. Furthermore, the user can view the sub-daily values of a specific day, by selecting the daily mean on the timeseries chart and then clicking the Show Sub-Daily button.

In addition to the timeseries chart, the user can also view the distributions of the predicted scores and observed streamflow, when available (Figure 23). Using this view, the user can interactively explore how the images change over changing flow, which can be useful to confirm that the model correctly predicts the relative ordering of images especially when observed flow data are not available.

When streamflow data are available, the user can explore the data with an interactive scatterplot of observed streamflow vs. predicted image scores (Figure 24). This chart is useful for identifying the causes of large model inaccuracies. For example, if a given point on the scatter plot is far from the 1:1 line, the user can see the image associated with that point, which often show visual quality issues (e.g., haze, glare, infrared mode, etc.).

Lastly, in addition to the interactive charts, the user can view more information about the model training and performance by viewing the model diagnostics, which is a PDF generated for each station. The diagnostics PDF contains the information about the annotations, training loss functions, Kendall's tau statistics, and various timeseries and scatterplots of observed and predicted values for different annotation and image splits. Appendix B contains an example diagnostic report for station West Brook 0_01171100.

Figure 22: Screenshot of FPE showing image and timeseries of daily mean predicted scores and observed streamflow at station West Brook 0_01171100.

Figure 23: Screenshot of FPE showing distribution chart of daily mean predicted scores and observed flows at station West Brook 0_0117100.

Figure 24: Screenshot of FPE showing scatterplot chart of daily mean predicted scores and observed flows at station West Brook 0_0117100.

5 Model Experiments

During this project, we performed three sets of model experiments. The first set focused on better understanding the effect of annotation quantity and quality on model training and performance. The other two explored potential extensions of the model by 1) integrating historical weather data along with the images to test the effect on model predictions, and 2) using a fine-tuning approach to train a new model at each station by using a single model pre-trained on multiple stations as a starting point.

5.1 Annotation Quantity and Quality

Two common questions we receive from users about the annotation process are:

1. How many annotations are needed to train a model at a new station?
2. How accurate do the annotations need to be?

To answer these questions, we performed a series of experiments that compared model performance across varying annotation dataset size and accuracy.

5.1.1 Number of Annotations

To determine how many annotations are needed to optimize model performance, we trained the model at two stations (Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000 and West Brook_0_01171100) using annotation datasets ranging in size from 50 image pairs up to the maximum number available at each station (2,500 and 5,000, respectively). We then compared the change in Kendall's tau of each model training iteration as a function of the number of training pairs (Figure 25). The results showed the largest increase in performance occurred from 50 to 200 pairs at each site. Between 200 and 1,000 pairs, further increases in tau were relatively small (approx. 0.04). Beyond 1,000 pairs, adding additional annotations resulted in very little change in tau. Therefore, for these two stations, we concluded that at least 200 annotated pairs are needed to achieve reasonable performance, with 1,000 pairs leading to near maximal performance. But any additional pairs would not lead to any appreciable gain in performance.

The values of Kendall's tau for each station also showed considerable variability between each successive iteration. This variability was primarily due to the randomness associated with sampling the specific pairs used for each dataset size. More research is needed to better understand the role of this variability, and how it might be minimized, as well as to repeat this process across more stations to develop more generalizable guidelines.

Figure 25: Changes in Kendall's tau with increasing annotation dataset size at Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000 and West Brook_0_01171100.

5.1.2 Annotation Accuracy

In addition to evaluating the number of annotations, we also looked at the effect of annotation accuracy on model performance. Using Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000, we ran a series of iterations where the accuracy of an annotation dataset containing 1,000 image pairs was artificially reduced from an initial accuracy of 85% down to 20%. The accuracy was changed by randomly switching the human-selected ranking (Left, Right, Same) across varying subsets of the dataset using logistic regression models to estimate the probability of annotation precision and accuracy based on the relative flow difference of each pair (see Section 4.2).

The results for Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000 showed relatively poor model performance ($\tau < 0.5$) for annotation accuracy below 50% (Figure 26). From accuracies of 50% to 75%, τ increased by approx. 0.2. And from 75% to 86%, there was relatively little increase in τ . Therefore, the results for this site suggest a minimum target accuracy of 60 – 75% to achieve strong model performance. Future research could expand on this experiment by performing multiple iterations of each accuracy to better understand the range of variability at each accuracy, as well as by repeating the experiment across other stations to create more generalizable guidance.

Figure 26: Change in Kendall's Tau with varying annotation accuracy at Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000.

Lastly, we also ran a series of trials at both Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000 and West Brook 0_01171100 to compare performance using the human annotations against “true” annotations, for which the pair ranking (left, right, same) were generated using the observed streamflow associated with the two images. For each station and trial, we used 1,000 image pairs sampled from the full set of available human annotations. The true annotations for that trial were then based on the same set of images as the human annotations, but with all labels re-assigned based on the true relative difference in flows. The experiment was repeated 5x at each station to assess the variability associated with random pair selection.

These results showed that even using a 100% accurate annotation dataset, the model performance was still limited to between 0.68 – 0.76 across the 5 trials at Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000 and 0.84 – 0.86 at West Brook 0_01171100. The increase in tau between the human annotations, which had accuracies of 75 – 79% at Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000 and 84 – 88% at West Brook 0_01171100, and the true annotations was limited to approx. 0.05 to 0.10 (Figure 27). In addition to showing the difference in tau between human and true annotations, the repeated trials also illustrate the degree of variability caused solely by differences across the random subsets of pairs sampled for each trial. These results thus show that annotation accuracy has a limited effect on model performance, at least for sufficiently accurate dataset ($\geq 75\%$ accuracy), and that annotation quality is not the only factor controlling the upper limit of model performance at a given station.

Figure 27: Repeated trials comparing Kendall's tau using human annotations vs. true annotations based on the observed flows of each image pair at Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000 and West Brook_0_01171100.

5.2 Weather Data Integration

In streams and rivers with natural flow regimes, the streamflow at a given location generally changes in response to recent precipitation or snow melt events that occur within its drainage area. High flows typically occur following rainstorms, and low flows occur during extended dry periods. The development of models for estimating streamflow rates based on weather data (i.e., rainfall runoff models) is one of the most widely studied areas of hydrology. We therefore explored modifying the RankNet model architecture to integrate historical weather data in conjunction with the timelapse images as two model input datasets.

Our expectation was that if the model can learn the relationship between weather and the responding streamflow alongside the visual information of the relative water level of the stream contained in the image, then it could potentially generate better streamflow estimates than using images alone. Furthermore, integration of weather data could potentially be beneficial when the quality of the image is poor (e.g., snow/ice cover, glare, haze, or other visual obstructions were present). Therefore, by providing two input datasets, we expected the model would be more robust than using the images alone.

The methodology and results of this investigation are provided in a separate technical memorandum (Walker, 2025), which is provided in Appendix C. A summary of the key findings include:

1. Contrary to our expectation, integration of weather data with the existing image model did not yield any appreciable improvement in model performance over the original model using only images, despite testing various architectures and approaches across a dozen different stations.
2. Independent testing of weather data model components using only weather data and without images showed that only one model structure (Fully Connect Network, FCN) demonstrated a strong ability to learn weather-flow relationships using even

relatively small datasets (n=500), which are common for the annotation datasets of FPE stations. The more sophisticated model structure (Long Short-Term Memory, LSTM) was unable to achieve even moderate performance except when using daily timeseries with a relatively large dataset of 5,000 observations. Using hourly timeseries, the LSTM model did not show any ability to learn patterns between weather and streamflow as it likely requires substantially larger training datasets.

Although these findings did not align with our expectations that adding weather data would improve model performance by providing the hydrologic context of image to the model, they are perhaps not surprising for a few reasons:

1. Accurately predicting instantaneous (e.g., 15-minute) flows from weather data is very challenging, especially in smaller headwater streams. The timing of hydrologic events (e.g., peak flows) can be especially difficult to predict, and can vary based on specific catchment characteristics, antecedent moisture conditions, and the intensity and spatial distribution of rainfall among other factors that vary across time and space.
2. Human activities and alterations of a watershed can have significant effects on expected rainfall-runoff relationships. Impoundments, which are common in the northeast and may include dam operations, can cause changes in flows independent of weather. These situations often confound any hydrologic model developed to accurately predict flows based solely on weather data.
3. The historical weather data used for these experiments were obtained from global climate reanalysis datasets at 9 km resolution. While these datasets are convenient as they can be used to obtain hourly data for any location in the world, they are likely less accurate at the small spatial scales needed to generate accurate rainfall-runoff relationships of headwater catchments. Furthermore, the streamflow at a given location on a stream or river depends not just on the weather at that specific location, but even more so on conditions across its entire drainage area. Using spatially distributed weather data at a higher spatial resolution that could then be aggregated across the drainage area of each station may improve these results.
4. Most of the FPE stations contained only 2 or 3 years of data, which may not be sufficient for the model to learn generalizable relationships between weather and flow that can be applied across years.

Overall, these findings suggest that while at least some deep learning models can learn associations between weather data and streamflow, adding those models to the existing RankNet image-based model did not yield sufficient improvement in model performance. More research is needed to explore alternative approaches to improve model performance such as (1) loss functions that account for image quality and help the model learn how to dynamically weight the image and weather data encoders, (2) use of spatially distributed weather datasets better reflecting conditions in the drainage area of each station, and (3) use of imagery datasets with longer periods of record.

5.3 Multi-Site Model Transferability

In addition to the integration of weather data, we also explored the transferability of models between stations. For these experiments, we trained a single model using images and measured streamflow data from 42 FPE stations located across the country. This so-called “base” model was trained using a regression strategy whereby the model learned to predict the actual flow of image, which is a different task from the rank-based training that is our standard method. The base model achieved strong performance in predicting the streamflow of a given image across all stations, with an overall $R^2 = 0.943$. When tested on an independent set of 11 stations not used for training, the model still performed moderately well with an $R^2 = 0.578$.

For each station, a new model was then trained by fine-tuning the multi-station base model using human annotations of paired image rankings at that station. The performance of these fine-tuned models was compared against predictions from the base model itself, as well as from standard RankNet models trained on only the image pair annotations (i.e., without fine-tuning). The results showed that for the test stations not used in base model training, the fine-tuned models performed slightly better than both the base model alone and standard RankNet models. Conversely, for the stations that were used to train the base model, fine-tuning generally performed slightly worse than using the base model itself likely due to the errors associated with human annotations. However, the fine-tuned model still performed better than the RankNet models based only on image pair annotations. Lastly, increasing the number of annotations from 200 to 500 pairs led to only slight improvements in performance for both standard and fine-tuned RankNet models.

From these experiments, we also learned that camera viewpoint and image quality appear to have stronger influences on model performance than the training approach. Stations with consistent upstream views of the full channel width performed best regardless of model and training algorithm, while those with lateral views, shifting angles, or visual obstructions performed more poorly. Stations facing downstream or laterally across the stream generally did not perform as well.

The methodology and results of these experiments are provided in more detail in the associated technical memorandum (Walker, 2025), which is included as Appendix C to this report.

6 Discussion and Conclusions

The results of this study demonstrate the effectiveness of using RankNet deep learning models trained with human annotations to monitor streamflow conditions using timelapse imagery. Across the 54 public stations where the model was applied, daily mean predictions showed strong correlation with observed streamflow, with Kendall's tau values ranging from 0.42 to 0.83 (median = 0.75). The model performed particularly well at stations where cameras provided consistent upstream views of the full channel width, enabling reliable visual assessment of relative streamflow conditions. These results validate the underlying premise that deep learning models can effectively learn to rank

images based on apparent streamflow conditions using only human-generated training data, without requiring direct streamflow measurements.

During this project, we identified several key limitations affecting model performance that should be considered when deploying this methodology at new locations. Camera perspective and stability emerged as critical factors, with stations experiencing multiple shifts in camera angle or field of view generally showing lower performance. Additionally, diurnal patterns in image quality posed significant challenges, particularly during winter months when shorter daylight hours resulted in more images being captured in low-light conditions or using infrared mode. Solar glare during certain times of day also created regular artifacts in the predictions, as demonstrated at station 29-West Brook 0_01171100 where afternoon glare consistently produced anomalous spikes in predicted scores. While annotator accuracy (median = 74.1%) and precision (median = 85.2%) were generally adequate for model training, stations with lower annotation quality tended to show reduced model performance, highlighting the importance of establishing and maintaining consistent annotation standards.

Our experiments with annotation quantity and quality yielded important insights for implementing this methodology at new stations. Results showed that at least 200 image pair annotations are needed to achieve reasonable model performance, with near-optimal performance reached with 1,000 pairs. Beyond these 1,000 pairs, the gains in performance were minimal, at least for the two stations used for these experiments. Annotation accuracy should target at least 60-75% to ensure robust model training, though higher accuracies did not necessarily yield proportional improvements in performance. These findings provide practical guidelines for efficiently collecting training data while maintaining sufficient quality standards.

The two sets of experiments for exploring 1) the integration of weather data alongside timelapse imagery, and 2) transferability of multi-site models did not yield any results suggesting substantial improvements in model performance from either approach. However, these experiments revealed valuable insights about the relative importance of image quality and camera perspective compared to other potential model enhancements.

Based on this study, we identified a few primary directions for future research that would improve on the current methodology. Development of automated image screening algorithms would be useful to help filter out low-quality images (e.g., night-time, glare, haziness) that currently introduce noise into the predictions. More sophisticated pair sampling strategies, potentially incorporating active learning approaches, could help optimize the annotation process by identifying the most informative image pairs for human review. Additionally, as the FPE platform expands to include other water body types beyond streams, the modeling framework may need to be adapted to handle different visual characteristics and hydrologic parameters. These enhancements will be particularly important as the methodology is applied to a wider range of monitoring scenarios and environmental conditions.

By developing this new methodology for training an AI/ML RankNet model to predict relative streamflow from timelapse images using only human annotations, this study has

played a critical role in advancing the FPE project. The modeling methodology developed in this project has been successfully integrated into the FPE platform, and provides an accessible resource for USEPA, USGS, and their project partners to monitor hydrologic conditions in streams and rivers using low-cost trail cameras to collect timelapse imagery. The estimated relative streamflow generated by these models and provided through FPE will support a wide range of hydrologic and ecological research, management, and decision making where traditional hydrologic monitoring (e.g., streamflow gauging) is infeasible or cost prohibitive. Overall, this project has led to a novel and widely accessible methodology that will greatly expand our ability to monitor hydrologic conditions across the country, helping to fill major data gaps such as the lack of streamflow data in smaller, headwater streams.

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Appendix A

FPE Stations for Model Training and Evaluation

Table A1: Locations and data availability of FPE stations having existing trained models. Number of images and annotations as well as start/end dates reflects data availability at time of model training. Excludes four stations marked as private.

Affiliation	Station	Latitude	Longitude	NWIS ID	# Daytime Images	Start	End	# Annotations	Has Obs. Flows
CT DEEP	34-Pendleton Hill Brook	41.4751	-71.8343	01118300	22,011	11/6/19	8/7/24	5,141	Y
CT DEEP	35-East Branch Eightmile River	41.4277	-72.3338	01194500	26,419	7/11/18	11/13/24	10,211	Y
CT DEEP	36-Mount Hope River	41.8430	-72.1689	01121000	20,229	5/15/19	8/5/24	1,915	Y
CT DEEP	201-Hubbard River	42.0376	-72.9395	01187300	13,299	6/23/21	11/8/23	3,380	Y
HALLORAN	58-North River at Frankton	42.6316	-72.7360	01169000	33,102	2/19/18	11/2/24	1,881	Y
MADER	7-Parkers Brook	42.3945	-72.0473		10,758	6/13/18	9/20/21	2,161	Y
MADER	8-Browns Brook	42.0341	-72.1602		10,581	1/9/19	1/27/22	7,792	Y
OWRB	105-North Canadian River near Wetumka	35.2645	-96.2071	07242000	8,581	10/25/22	3/25/24	2,013	Y
OWRB	116-Little River near Sasakwa	34.9653	-96.5120	07231000	11,140	1/9/23	9/16/24	2,236	Y
OWRB	146-Red River near Terral	33.8778	-97.9343	07315500	9,509	4/17/23	10/28/24	3,194	Y
USEPA	237-Dunnfield Creek AN0012	40.9714	-75.1266		5,534	7/20/23	10/29/24	1,835	
USGS	71-01342797_Vly Brook	43.3928	-74.8328		26,935	10/12/22	5/16/24	4,662	
USGS	80-01359135_Patroun Creek	42.6634	-73.7449	01359135	27,746	10/12/22	5/17/24	4,887	Y
USGS	89-01349711_West Kill	42.1850	-74.2769	01349711	19,718	10/13/22	1/31/24	4,411	Y
USGS	90-01421618_Town Brook	42.3611	-74.6622	01421618	21,687	10/25/22	2/28/24	4,619	Y
USGS	95-01362342_Lanesville	42.1422	-74.2650	01362342	6,381	10/5/22	3/20/24	5,185	Y
USGS CMWSC	178-NF Vermilion River	40.8356	-88.2989	05554000	8,020	4/20/23	4/30/24	4,927	
USGS CMWSC	179-Colfax	40.5573	-88.6103	05564190	8,393	4/12/23	4/30/24	4,594	
USGS CO-WSC	154-Mill Creek	39.6402	-106.3729	393814106221500	8,339	2/9/23	5/23/24	723	
USGS CO-WSC	158-Gore Creek abv Red Sst Creek	39.6409	-106.3943	09066325	5,932	2/10/23	5/22/24	2,034	Y
USGS CONTE	9-Sanderson Brook_01171010	42.4364	-72.6868		46,826	4/1/21	3/22/24	4,821	Y
USGS CONTE	10-West Brook Lower_01171090	42.4319	-72.6642		56,080	2/27/19	4/9/24	2,256	Y
USGS CONTE	11-West Brook Upper_01171030	42.4375	-72.6760	01171030	31,097	1/3/20	11/23/22	2,101	
USGS CONTE	12-Avery Brook_Bridge_01171000	42.4498	-72.6944	01171000	41,241	3/10/21	4/2/24	3,147	Y
USGS CONTE	13-Avery Brook_Side_01171000	42.4499	-72.6939	01171000	39,871	3/19/21	4/2/24	2,441	Y
USGS CONTE	14-Avery Brook_River Right_01171000	42.4498	-72.6936	01171000	47,222	3/19/21	4/2/24	2,214	Y
USGS CONTE	15-Avery Brook_River Left_01171000	42.4499	-72.6937	01171000	47,943	7/2/21	4/2/24	2,277	Y
USGS CONTE	16-West Brook Reservoir_01171020	42.4371	-72.6834		39,355	3/25/21	3/22/24	2,325	Y
USGS CONTE	17-West Whately_01171005	42.4568	-72.6882		49,414	4/6/21	4/9/24	2,510	Y
USGS CONTE	18-Obear Brook Lower_01171070	42.4343	-72.6715		42,629	3/30/21	3/7/24	1,959	Y
USGS CONTE	29-West Brook 0_01171100	42.4143	-72.6293	01171100	31,816	2/1/22	4/2/24	7,953	Y
USGS CONTE	41-Dry Brook Upper	42.6683	-72.5053		49,032	5/11/22	12/6/24	2,473	
USGS CONTE	65-Green River_01170100	42.7034	-72.6708	01170100	23,231	9/29/22	3/29/24	5,057	Y
USGS CONTE	68-West Branch Swift River_01174565	42.4551	-72.3818	01174565	28,388	9/14/17	3/28/24	3,553	Y
USGS CONTE	145-West Brook Upper_New23_01171030	42.4375	-72.6760	01171030	18,086	4/21/23	5/9/24	2,485	
USGS EESC	44-PA_01FL	38.2092	-78.7527		23,532	5/17/22	10/17/24	1,545	Y
USGS EESC	45-PA_05FL	38.1971	-78.7687		22,778	5/17/22	8/24/24	1,621	
USGS EESC	46-PA_06FL	38.1974	-78.7737		23,144	5/17/22	3/8/24	4,899	Y
USGS EESC	51-SR_02FL	38.4630	-78.4101		17,957	5/18/22	4/22/24	3,367	
USGS EESC	52-SR_04FL	38.4584	-78.3995		19,478	5/18/22	5/3/24	1,873	
USGS EESC	53-SR_06FL	38.4565	-78.3809		14,883	5/19/22	4/30/24	3,939	
USGS EESC	54-SR_09FL	38.4464	-78.3759		14,798	5/19/22	4/30/24	4,434	Y
USGS EESC	72-PA_04.5FL	38.1982	-78.7673		17,156	9/13/22	5/13/24	4,973	
USGS EESC	73-PI_06.5FL	38.7197	-78.2807		20,147	9/14/22	4/24/24	1,949	
USGS EESC	74-PI_08.5FL	38.7089	-78.2745		19,776	9/14/22	5/16/24	1,973	

Table A1: Locations and data availability of FPE stations having existing trained models. Number of images and annotations as well as start/end dates reflects data availability at time of model training. Excludes four stations marked as private.

Affiliation	Station	Latitude	Longitude	NWIS ID	# Daytime Images	Start	End	# Annotations	Has Obs. Flows
USGS EESC	75-PA_06.5FL	38.1972	-78.7755		18,031	5/17/22	4/23/24	1,760	
USGS NJWSC	81-01379530 Canoe Brook near Summit NJ	40.7444	-74.3536	01379530	69,865	10/20/22	4/4/24	4,778	Y
USGS NJWSC	131-01456100 Hatchery Brook at Hackettstown, NJ	40.8549	-74.8348	01456100	17,875	4/7/23	4/13/24	1,898	
USGS NYWSC	242-Biscuit Brook above Confluence	41.9876	-74.5014		22,480	6/14/23	9/24/24	1,669	
USGS PAWSC	123-Fishing Creek, 01573660	40.1533	-76.7556	01573660	20,970	3/10/23	6/6/24	4,959	Y
USGS PAWSC	166-Chiques Creek, 01575900	40.0628	-76.5158	01575900	17,258	6/22/23	6/15/24	5,139	Y
USGS-NVWSC	257-TROY CYN NR NYALA, NV	38.3492	-115.5899	10247170	18,691	9/27/23	10/21/24	1,956	

Appendix B

Example Model Diagnostics Report for
West Brook 0_01171100

FPE Rank Model Diagnostics

Created: 2024-04-12 12:52:08.237697
Station: West Brook 0_01171100 (id=29)
Model: RANK-FLOW-20240410

Images:
Start: 2022-02-01 13:00:00
End: 2024-04-02 12:45:00
Images: 31,933

Annotations:
Source: human
Train Pairs: 6365
Val Pairs: 1588
Period: 2022-02-01 to 2023-09-30
Notes:

Training:
Epochs: 20
Learn Rate: 0.001

Performance (Kendall Tau):
Train: 0.85
Val: 0.85
Test (In): 0.83
Test (Out): 0.74
Test (All): 0.80
Overall: 0.82

Input Data

Images

Timeseries of Obs. Flow and Image Splits

Obs. Flow Distributions by Image Split

Annotations

Model Training

Loss Function

Model Predictions

Timeseries

Timeseries of Observed Flow, Predited Scores, Percentile Ranks, and Z Scores

Scatter Plots

Obs Flow vs Pred Score

Obs vs. Pred Ranks

Obs vs. Pred Z Scores

Split
• Train
• Val
• Test (In)
• Test (Out)

Residuals

Timeseries of Percentile Rank Residuals (Obs - Pred)

Daily Aggregation

Note: Daily mean values computed using only daytime images (7AM-7PM)

Performance (Kendall Tau):

Train:	0.87
Val:	0.86
Test (In):	0.86
Test (Out):	0.84
Test (All):	0.84
Overall:	0.85

Daily Timeseries of Observed and Predicted Ranks

Observed vs. Predicted Daily Ranks

Appendix C

Weather Data Integration and Model Transferability Memo

Due to its size, this appendix is provided as a separate file named:

Walker2025 - FPE ROAR Year 1 Report - Appendix C - 20250403.pdf

This file can be accessed at the report repository: [10.5281/zenodo.15133342](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15133342)